

Does Women Representation on Boards and Audit Committees Restrict Earnings Management? The Impact of Family Ownership in Malaysian Firms

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Abstract

We examine whether the representation of women on the boards and the audit committees is associated with a reduction in earnings management. We also observe if family ownership moderates the relationship between women on boards (and audit committees) and earnings management. Examining Bursa Malaysia listed firms in 2008, we show that the presence of women on the boards and audit committees would restrict earnings management. This is especially so for non-family-owned firms, but for family-owned firms such evidence was not found. This suggests that women outperform men in the accounting oversight role when control from family members is minimal.

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1. Introduction

The issue of earnings quality and management has been the subject of intense research following corporate financial failures and frauds such as those of Enron and WorldCom in 2002. The series of financial scandals has weakened stakeholders' confidence in corporate governance because a weak corporate governance mechanism is responsible for the practice of earnings management. The term 'earnings quality' refers to the degree to which the reported earnings reflect the economic reality of a company. One of the factors that can jeopardize earnings quality is 'earnings management'. Earnings management occurs when managers use their discretion in adopting the accounting methods or techniques that will produce the desired earnings, and in so doing they mislead their stakeholders.

A number of studies examined whether the corporate governance mechanisms of Malaysian companies are able to mitigate earnings management (Abdullah & Mohd Nasir, 2004; Mohd Saleh et al., 2005 and 2007; and Abdul Rahman & Mohamed Ali, 2006). One corporate governance characteristic that has received growing attention is gender diversity in top management. It is argued that women's representation in top management would alleviate the practice of earnings management. Women are believed to have higher ethical values (Betz et al., 1989) and are more risk averse than men in handling money matters (Krishnan & Parsons, 2008). Because of the inconclusive results and the gap in the literature, we examine if the participation of women on the board of directors and the audit committee mitigate the practice of earnings management in listed companies in Malaysia.

We also examine if family ownership would reduce the tendency of women directors to mitigate earnings management. Family-owned companies are more likely to appoint women directors who are family members. This practice is less likely to restrict the practice of earnings management because the family-related female directors would be more dependent on the top management and the firms, and hence are less effective in monitoring (Anderson & Reeb, 2003; Abdullah et al. 2012). This study is significant because the issue of women holding top

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posts has become an important topic in recent years. In 2004, the Government adopted a policy to appoint 30% women to the decision-making levels in the public sector, and in 2011, the policy is extended to the private sector.

2. Gender, leadership, and attitudes towards ethics and risks

Srinidhi et al. (2011) point out that women are different from men in their leadership styles and attitudes towards ethics and risks. Unlike men, women show greater concern for interpersonal relationships and rely on rules of fairness. Whereas men adopt the 'transactional' or command-and-control approach of leadership, women tend to adopt the 'transformational', interactive or the participative approach of leadership. In the transactional approach, leaders regard job performance as a series of transactions with subordinates in which the latter is rewarded for services rendered and punished for unacceptable performance. On the other hand, transformational leaders transform the self-interest of their subordinates into the interest of the group. This leadership approach encourages participation, shares power and information, enhances the self-worth of others and energizes subordinates (Rosener, 1990). Women would rather be evaluated on the basis of employee satisfaction than on the basis of financial performance (Appelbaum & Shapiro, 1993). Based on these leadership traits, it is argued that women are less likely to manage earnings.

It is a widespread belief that women are more risk averse than men in making financial decisions. It is also a general belief that men are more confident than women in dealing with financial matters, and women are more likely to avoid competition. Although findings are mixed, there is evidence to support these beliefs. A survey of fund managers in the US, Germany, Italy, and Thailand found that women are more risk averse, tend to be less overconfident and are more likely to avoid competition (Beckmann & Menkhoff, 2008). Fehr-Duda (2006), Watson and McNaughton (2007) and Eckel and Grossman (2008) also found that women are more risk averse than men. Since earnings management is associated with risks, we believe that women are less likely to be involved in earnings management.

The gender socialization approach argues that men and women bring different values into their workplace that will subsequently shape their decisions and practices (Betz et al., 1989). Since men regard money and advancement as their success factors, and see achievement as competition, Betz et al. (1989) argue that men are more likely than women, to break rules or to be less ethical. Women, who show less concern for money and advancement, are more likely to adhere to rules and laws. The results of research that examines the association between gender and ethics are mixed. However, some empirical evidence indicates that men are more likely to engage in unethical behaviors (see for example, Albaum & Peterson, 2006; Betz et al., 1989).

3. Hypothesis development

Early studies use the attitudinal survey method to examine the association between earnings management and gender. Clikeman et al. (2001) and Al-Hayale and Lan (2005) reveal that male and female respondents show similar attitudes towards earnings management. However, the survey of students and business managers in the US by Giocomino et al. (2006) provides evidence that women tend to have a stricter view on earnings management compared to men.

Since the attitudes of students do not reflect the actual behavior of managers facing actual business situations, the method has its limitations as far as reliability is concerned (Krishnan & Parsons, 2008). Only recently that researchers observe the financial reports in examining the association between gender and earnings management. Krishnan and Parsons (2008) found that the participation of women in senior management is able to improve the quality of earnings. In their study of S&P 500 firms, Peni and Vahamaa (2010) examine the association between earnings management and gender of firms' executives (CEOs and CFOs). They found that firms with female CFOs are associated with income-decreasing discretionary accruals, implying that female CFOs follow more conservative earnings management strategies. Srinidhi et al. (2011) examined the association between female board membership and earnings quality among firms in the US. They provide evidence that companies having female representation in top management are associated with a lower incidence of earnings management practice.

Nevertheless, Sun et al. (2011), in their study of S&P 500 firms did not find any association between the proportion of women directors on the audit committee and earnings management. They argue that men and women may have the same ethical beliefs towards earnings management. They also believe that even though female directors may be more ethical than men may, the former just could not influence the rest of the committee members. Drawing on the perspectives of leadership, ethical values and attitudes towards risks discussed above, and prior empirical evidence, we hypothesize the following:

H1: Boards of directors (audit committees) with female representation are less likely to engage in earnings management.

We further expect that family ownership will weaken the influence of women directors at reducing earnings management. Family-firms are typically risk-averse and are more likely to nominate board members (including women) from amongst family members (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Anderson & Reeb, 2003; and Abdullah et al., 2012). This practice will weaken the quality of earnings because the family-member directors would be more dependent on the top management of the firms and thus are less effective in discharging their monitoring roles (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The nomination exercise also restricts the pool of potential candidates, which in the case of women is typically small. With a smaller pool of candidates to select from, there is greater likelihood of nominating lesser qualified women (Siegel et al., 2011; Abdullah et al., 2012).

In addition, the variety of views that gender diversity brings to the board are likely to be of lesser value in an environment where the need to maintain family relationships and unity is critical in order to secure the family's survival (Bertrand & Schoar, 2006). In family-firms, gender diversity may jeopardize board discussions and diminish their effectiveness (Phillips et al., 2009; Carter et al., 2010), hampering the initiatives to improve the quality of earnings. Based on the above arguments, we hypothesized that:

H2: Family ownership negatively moderates the relationship between female representation on boards (audit committees) and earnings management.

4. Research methods

Data for the year 2008 is collected from all companies listed on the Bursa Malaysia, except for finance, close-end funds, and real estate investment trust (REIT) companies. Information on boards of directors and other non-financial information are gathered from the annual reports of the sample firms, while financial data is gathered from Datastream. To test the hypothesis, we conduct two separate hierarchical regression analyses (one for women directorship, and the other for women audit committee). The structural equations are as follows:

$$DACC = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 WOMDIR + \beta_2 FAMOWN + \beta_3 WOMDIR * FAMOWN + \sum_{i=4}^n \beta_i X + \epsilon, \quad (1)$$

$$DACC = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 WOMAC + \beta_2 FAMOWN + \beta_3 WOMAC * FAMOWN + \sum_{i=4}^n \beta_i X + \epsilon, \quad (2)$$

where, DACC = discretionary accruals; WOMDIR = 1 if a board has at least one female director, 0 otherwise; WOMAC = 1 if an audit committee has at least one female director, 0 otherwise; FAMOWN = family ownership, 1 if a family owns at least 20% of shares in a company, 0 otherwise; and X = a vector of control variables, i.e. board independence (BODIND), board size (BODSIZE), company size (COSIZE), audit committee size (ACSIZE), audit committee accounting expertise (ACEXPT), profitability (ROA), leverage (LEV), auditor size (AUDITOR), and five main industry classifications (industrial products (INDPR), consumer products (CONPR), trading and services (TRADE), property (PROP), and construction (CONSTR)).

Board independence is the proportion of independent directors, board size is the total number of board members, and company size is the natural log of total assets. As for auditor size, a score of 1 is given if a company is audited by a Big-4 auditor, and 0 otherwise. The number of members and the number of accounting experts in the

committee, respectively, measure audit committee size and expertise. We expect that all these variables will have a negative relationship with earnings management. The return on assets (ROA) is the ratio of net income to total assets. Profitability is predicted to be negatively associated with earnings management because managers are expected to adjust earnings via accruals due to the threat of dismissal or not receiving a bonus. Leverage is the ratio of total debt to total assets and it is a measure of the risk of breaching debt covenants. The coefficient is predicted to be positive. A dummy variable is used to identify companies into their industry classification.

Earnings management is measured using working capital accruals (also referred to as current accruals). Manipulation through working capital accruals is very attractive because it has no direct cash flow consequences and is relatively difficult to detect and easier for managers to manage (Xie et al., 2003; Peasnell et al., 2005). Further, managers have greater discretion in managing current accruals than long-term accruals (Guenther, 1994; Teoh et al., 1998).

5. Results and discussion

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables included in the study. The number of firms that appoint women to their audit committees is much lesser, with only 17% of the firms having women on the committee, indicating that 40% of those companies with women on boards appoint women to their audit committees. Although the percentage is not high, it is acceptable because women only occupy on average about one out of seven or eight board seats in a company that has women on its board.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics (n=639)

Panel A: Continuous variables					
Variable	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Skewness
Discretionary Accrual (DACC)	-1.08	1.02	0.04	0.14	0.24
Board Independence (BODIND)	0.22	0.92	0.44	0.12	0.84
Board size (BODSIZE)	3	17	7.46	1.86	0.89
Company Size (COSIZE)	10.04	18.07	12.88	1.34	0.86
Audit committee size (ACSIZE)	2	9	3.27	.63	2.95
Audit com. expertise (ACEXPT)	0	4	1.08	.64	0.55
Return on assets (ROA)	-0.88	0.74	0.033	0.96	-0.64
Leverage (LEV)	0.48	176.81	4.04	8.09	16.16

Panel B: Dummy variables		
Variable	Yes (1)	No (0)
Women on Board (WOMBD)	274 (43%)	365 (57%)
Women on Audit Committee (WOMAC)	109 (17%)	530 (83%)
Family ownership (FAMOWN)	157 (25%)	482 (75%)
Auditor (BIG4)	57 (57%)	277 (43%)
Industry sector:		
Industrial Products (INDPR)	212 (33%)	427 (67%)
Consumer Products (CONPR)	119 (19%)	520 (81%)
Trade and services (TRADE)	136 (21%)	503 (79%)
Property (PROP)	71 (11%)	568 (89%)
Construction (CONSTR)	38 (6%)	601 (94%)

Table 2 presents the results from the hierarchical regression analyses using WOMBD and WOMAC separately as the main variables. Results in all models show that the presence of women on the boards and the audit committees do have an influence at curbing the practice of accrual management. The negative correlations between DACC and WOMBD as well as WOMAC show that boards of directors and audit committees with female representation are less likely to engage in earnings management. Our evidence is consistent with those of Krishnan and Parsons (2008), Srinidhi et al. (2011) and Peni and Vahamaa (2010), and thus support Hypotheses 1.

Table 2: Model Estimates: Regression Coefficients (t-values) N=639

	WOMBD as main variable				WOMAC as main variable			
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8
Constant	.069 (1.068)	.073 (1.129)	.072 (1.110)	.077 (1.197)	.069 (1.068)	.072 (1.113)	.071 (1.104)	.067 (1.038)
WOMBD (WOMAC)		-.018* (-1.725)	-.018* (-1.741)	-.030** (-2.438)		-.030** (-2.218)	-.030** (-2.217)	-.046*** (-2.908)
FAMOWN			.003 (.251)	-.020 (-1.136)			.001 (.088)	-.010 (-.719)
WOMBD*FAMOWN (WOMAC*FAMOWN)				.045* (1.861)				.061* (1.953)
BODIND	.019 (.401)	.017 (.363)	.019 (.390)	.019 (.400)	.019 (.401)	.020 (.426)	.021 (.433)	.025 (.518)
BODSIZE	-.001 (-.396)	.000 (-.174)	.001 (.175)	-.000 (-.020)	-.001 (-.396)	-.001 (-.436)	-.001 (-.437)	-.001 (-.275)
ACSIZE	.008 (.856)	.008 (.828)	.008 (.828)	.008 (.864)	.008 (.856)	.010 (1.049)	.010 (1.049)	.010 (1.070)
ACEXPRT	.009 (1.083)	.008 (1.042)	.009 (1.050)	.009 (1.145)	.009 (1.083)	.009 (1.127)	.009 (1.128)	.009 (1.096)
COSIZE	-.007 (-1.463)	-.007 (-1.506)	-.007 (-1.510)	-.007 (-1.612)	-.007 (-1.463)	-.007 (-1.547)	-.007 (-1.547)	-.007 (-1.517)
ROA [§]	-.002 (-.388)	-.002 (-.266)	-.002 (-.257)	-.001 (-.160)	-.002 (-.388)	-.002 (-.325)	-.002 (-.323)	-.002 (-.268)
LEV [§]	-.013** (-2.171)	-.013** (-2.060)	-.013** (-2.067)	-.013** (-2.157)	-.013** (-2.171)	-.013** (-2.119)	-.013** (-2.119)	-.013** (-2.105)
BIG4	-.009 (-.866)	-.009 (-.836)	-.009 (-.854)	-.008 (-.752)	-.009 (-.866)	-.008 (-.752)	-.008 (-.756)	-.008 (-.795)
INDPR	-.007 (-.342)	-.004 (-.197)	-.004 (-.189)	-.005 (-.286)	-.007 (-.342)	-.005 (-.273)	-.005 (-.271)	-.006 (-.291)
CONPR	.160*** (7.730)	.163*** (7.857)	.163*** (7.852)	.161*** (7.732)	.160*** (7.730)	.160*** (7.715)	.160*** (7.708)	.159*** (7.670)
TRADE	-.006 (-.316)	-.003 (-.162)	-.003 (-.134)	-.004 (-.188)	-.006 (-.316)	-.006 (-.277)	-.005 (-.267)	-.005 (-.269)
PROP	.001 (.034)	.005 (.235)	.006 (.244)	.004 (.174)	.001 (.034)	.000 (.015)	.000 (.017)	-.001 (-.039)
CONSTR	.107*** (3.946)	.109*** (4.003)	.108*** (3.992)	.105*** (3.882)	.107*** (3.946)	.111*** (4.097)	.111*** (4.090)	.106*** (3.907)
R ²	0.237	0.241	0.241	0.245	0.237	0.243	0.243	0.248
Adj. R ²	0.221	0.224	0.223	0.226	0.221	0.226	0.225	0.228
F statistic	14.943***	14.132	13.175***	12.616***	14.943***	14.314***	13.338***	12.800***

We also find that family ownership positively moderates the relationship between earnings management and women on boards and audit committees (Models 4 and 8). In line with Hypotheses 2, it is less likely that women directors in family-owned companies would restrict earnings management compared to women in non-family-owned companies. This indicates that women are more effective in exercising their roles as monitors and act ethically in an environment where they are free from the influence of family members. Women would not be able to act in the best interest of the shareholders and would not add value in family-owned firms because family survival would very much depend on family relationships and unity (Bertrand & Schoar, 2006). We also find that the industry variables have a bearing in influencing earnings management. Contrary to our expectation, we found that highly-leveraged firms are less likely to manage earnings compared to their lower counterparts. One interpretation is that debt providers also might use other information in addition to the accounting numbers when monitoring the ability of the borrowers to service their debts. Hence, there is less earnings management in these firms. We do not find any association between board independence and earnings management, a finding consistent with those of Abdullah and Mohd Nasir (2004), Abdul Rahman and Mohamed Ali (2006), and Hashim and Devi (2008).

6. Conclusion

We provide evidence that companies with women on top management would perform better in mitigating earnings management than those without, thus supporting the contention that women are more ethical and stricter than men when it comes to financial matters. In addition, our study shows that women are less likely to curb the practice of earnings management in family-owned companies than in non-family owned companies. One explanation is that family firms are more likely to appoint women in their family members, irrespective of their skills and qualification, who tend to act in the interest of the family members in order to secure their family's survival. Serving on the boards of family-owned companies is thus a challenging role for a non-family member woman director because of the limitation that she has to face in exercising her monitoring role as a director. This opens up avenues for future research as far as women directors in family-owned companies is concerned.

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